

Organizational Silence: Its Devastating Role of Organizational Success

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this research is to identify the effects of organizational silence on organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Design/methodology/approach: To assess organizational silence, refer to (organizational silence questionnaire, Schechtman, 2008; Brinsfield, 2009), and organizational success (organizational success questionnaire Simon et al., 2011). Out of the 372 questionnaires that were distributed to employees, 315 usable questionnaires were returned, a response rate of 84%. Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used to confirm the research hypotheses.

Findings: The research has found that there is significant relationship between organizational silence and organizational success and found that organizational silence directly affects on organizational success. In other words, organizational silence is one of the biggest barriers to organizational success of the employees at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Practical implications: This research pointed to the need for organizations to adopt a culture which encourages and urges employees to speak in the labor issues and the non-silence in order for the administration to be able to realize these issues and try to solve them first hand in order to prevent their aggravation.

Originality/value: Silence climate has an impact on the ability of organizations to detect errors and learn. Therefore, organizational effectiveness is negatively affected. This research aims to measure the effect of organizational silence on organizational success. Based on the findings of this research, some important implications are discussed.

Keywords: organizational silence, organizational success

1. Introduction

Organizations need employees who express their ideas; employees also choose organizations in which they can express themselves because both employees and managers have high motivation and high performance in a place that silence doesn't exist (Beheshtifar et al., 2012).

Researchers have been interested in silence and voice related concepts. Employees often have ideas, information and opinions for constructive ways to improve work and work organizations. Sometimes these employees practice voice and express their ideas, information, and opinions; and other times they remain silent and withhold their ideas, information, and opinions. Apparently, expressing and withholding behaviors might appear to be polar opposites because silence implies not speaking while voice implies speaking up on important issues and problems in organizations (Zehir & Erdogan, 2011).

Employees have an important role in success and failure in an organization. Employee Silence (ES) causes to a negative organizational atmosphere in occurring of new ideas, exhibition of talents and information share, and this means a significant danger for organizational. Thus, it is quite important in creation in an organization if the employees stay silent or not in making decisions about opportunities (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

ES and organizational success are very important subjects for organizations to reach desired objectives. The study is structured as follows: Section one is introductory. Section two presents the literature review. Section three discusses the research model. Section four presents the research questions and hypotheses. Section five explains the research strategy. Empirical results will take place at section six. Section seven handles the main findings of the research. Finally, recommendations will be provided at the last section.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Silence

Silence is as omission of vocal or written expression of cognitive or emotional evaluation that can change or improve organizational conditions (Morrison & Milliken, 2000; Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

Different researchers discuss silence from different perspectives. Morrison and Milliken (2000) reviewed silence as a collective phenomenon at the organizational level, while other researchers such as Ashford et. al., (1998), Zhou & George (2001) approach it as an individual phenomenon (Bowen & Blackmon, 2003).

Silence is viewed by many researchers as the absence of speech (Van Dyne et. al., 2003). Silence is most often associated with a group dynamic (Zerubavel, 2006).

Remaining silent in an organization limits knowledge sharing, collective brainstorming, problem identification, and possible solutions to workplace-related issues. This also generates new problems (Bowen

& Blackmon, 2003). This behavior needs to be stopped before it becomes endemically cultural and destructive to the organization (Ellis & Dyne, 2009).

Silence is not simply defined as the opposite of voice in the sense that we cannot qualify silence and voice with just the act or absence of speaking up (Gambarotto & Cammozzo, 2010).

Silence can convey approval and sharing or disfavor and opposition, thus becoming a pressure mechanism for both individuals and organizations (Bagheri, et al. 2012).

2.2. Types of Silence

There are four types of silence. They are acquiescent silence, defensive silence, prosocial silence, and protective silence (Pinder & Harlos 2001; Van Dyne, et al., 2003; Briensfield 2009; Perlow & Repeating; 2009; Cakici 2010; Alparslan 2010; Bogosian, 2012).

2.2.1. Acquiescent Silence

Acquiescent silence (AS) relates to occasions where employees chose not to express relevant ideas, information and opinions based on resignation which suggests disengaged behaviour (Kahn 1990).

AS is synonymous with employees who are essentially disengaged and are unwilling to take steps to enact change (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

AS is described as an intentionally passive silent behavior. AS is withholding relevant ideas, information, or opinions, based on resignation. AS suggests disengaged behavior that is more passive than active (Van Dyne, et al. 2003).

AS is the withholding of information, views, opinions and ideas in the face of developments in the organizations.

AS is a passive behavior. In the case of AS, employees approve the status quo, do not want to speak up much, and do not attempt to change the organizational circumstances. This attitude requires remaining silent purposefully and not being involved in developments. The reason that lies behind employees' failure to speak out is the belief that it will not make a difference even if they do speak out (Karacaoglu & Cingoz, 2008).

2.2.2. Defensive Silence

Defensive silence (DS) is based on an employee's personal fear of speaking up. This can be termed as quiescent silence (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

DS is described as deliberate omission of work related information based on fear of reprisal. DS is intentional and proactive behavior that is intended to protect the self from external threats. In contrast to AS, DS is more proactive, involving awareness and consideration of alternatives, followed by a conscious decision to withhold ideas, information, and opinions as the best personal strategy at the moment. DS differs from the previous form in that defensive silence involves the individual weighing up the alternatives and making a conscious choice to withhold ideas information and opinions as the safest option for the individual at that point in time (Van Dyne, et al., 2003).

DS is a proactive and conscious behavior with the urge of self-protection against external threats (Karacaoglu & Cingoz, 2008).

2.2.3. Pro Social Silence

Prosocial silence is withholding of work related information for the benefit of others including the organization. Pro-social silence as intentional and proactive behaviour is primarily focused on others. Pro-social silence involves conscious decision making by an employee. Pro-social silence arises from a concern for others instead of fear of negative personal consequences (Korsgaard et al., 1997).

Pro social silence is the refusal to express ideas information or opinions so that others in the organization might benefit from it. This silence is motivated by the desire to help others and share the duties. It is considerate and focuses on others (Podkasoff et al., 2000).

Pro social Silence is withholding work-related ideas, information, or opinions with the goal of benefiting other people or the organization-based on altruism or cooperative motives. This form of silence is intentional, proactive and other-oriented. In other words, primary priority of an employee who decides to remain silent is not himself but the external factors such as the organization or his colleagues (Van Dyne et.al., 2003).

Like Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), pro-social silence is intentional and proactive behavior that is primarily focused on others. Like OCB, pro-social silence is discretionary behavior that can not be mandated by an organization. Like DS, pro-social silence is based on awareness and consideration of alternatives and the conscious decision to withhold ideas, information, and opinions. In contrast to DS, pro-social silence is motivated by concern for others, rather than by fear of negative personal consequences that might occur from speaking up (Van Dyne, et al. 2003).

2.2.4. Protective Silence

Protective silence is where employees can be silent and accept decisions of higher level management. One of the most important causes of silence is the good relationship between the organization and employees. Therefore, employees prefer to be silent instead of telling what is wrong in their organizations. For that reason silent employees never share their opinion to solve conflict in the organization (Morrison & Milliken, 2003; Perlow & Repenning, 2009, Alparslan 2010).

2.3. Organizational Silence

Organizational silence has been mostly discussed in public administration literature (Tangirala & Ramanujam, 2008; Ozdemir et al., 2013).

Organizational silence can remain prevalent when management proudly speak of empowerment and the development of more open lines communication (Lawler 1992; Spreitzer 1996).

Organizational silence has been defined as “consciously refrain from expressing ideas, information and beliefs about work.” Organizational silence may result in lack of feedback, information and ideas and alternatives analysis and thus the organization is damaged from organizational processes of low effectiveness. Organizational silence occurs when employees intentionally withhold their opinions and knowledge about organizational problems. In other words, employees might prefer to withhold their knowledge, ideas and suggestions, which might promote organizational development (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

Organizational silence is a reaction of employees; although they are normally able to bring and sustain change to workplace, they remain reluctant to share their behavioral, cognitive, or emotional assessments on workplace related issues. In other words, Organizational silence is the withholding of any form of genuine expression about the individual's behavioral, cognitive and/or affective evaluations of his or her organizational circumstances to persons who are perceived to be capable of effecting change or redress (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

Organizational silence means that the employee withholds his opinions and suggestions about the work of the organization problems (Pinder & Harlos, 2001). Organizational silence means the presence of a common perception among employees limiting their participation in providing their knowledge about the issues and policies of the Organization (Nennete, 2002).

Organizational silence is deliberate prevention of information and opinions by the staff of the organization (Van Dyne, et al, 2003).

Organizational silence occurs due to the fundamental beliefs held by managers including; manager's fear of negative feedback and a set of implicit beliefs held by managers that lead to organizational structures, processes and managerial practices that impede the level of silence within an organization (Rodriguez, 2004).

Organizational silence refers to the employee's failure to participate views and suggestions on important labor issues and choosing to remain silent (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

Organizational silence refers to the collective phenomenon of comment or to very little action in response to the major issues facing the organization (Henriksen & Dayton, 2006).

Organizational silence is a variable which can prevail about barriers to effectiveness, commitment and performance (Beer 2009).

Organizational silence is a behavioral choice that can deteriorate or improve organizational performance. Excluding its emotionally difficult expression, silence can convey approval and sharing or disfavor and opposition, thus becoming a pressure mechanism for both individuals and organizations (Gambarotto & Cammozzo, 2010).

Organizational silence can be beneficial in some cases, these are: decrease of administrative information overload, reducing interpersonal conflicts and storage of secret information. Despite these,

organizational silence is rather regarded as a harmful phenomenon for both the employee and the organization (Tikici et al., 2011).

Organizational silence leads to dissonance and this in turn result in low motivation, satisfaction and commitment. Also, other evidence suggests that ES can lead to stress, denial, dissatisfaction and disconnection between the staff. In addition, organizational silence makes the employees feel that they are unvalued and think that they don't have control over their work (Nikolaou et al., 2011).

Organizational silence is an inefficient process which can waste all organizational efforts and may take various forms, such as collective silence in meetings, low levels of participation in suggestion schemes, low levels of collective voice and so on (Nikmaram, et al., 2012).

2.4. Organizational Silence Factors

There are some factors of organizational silence. They are as follows: (1) support of the top management of silence, (2) lack of communication opportunities, (3) support of supervisor for silence, (4) official authority, and (5) the subordinate's fear of negative reactions (Brinsfield, 2009).

2.4.1. Support of the Top Management of Silence

The role of top management is instrumental in the success of the business organizations. The availability of a high degree of confidence in the administration reduces concerns of speaking freely about the problems and issues of labor. Climate of confidence in the top management reduces the feelings of uncertainty (Weber & Weber, 2001). On the other hand, the attitudes and values of the top management may contribute greatly to the formation of a climate of silence, as some organizations prohibit employees from saying what they know or feel (Argyris, 1997).

The top management practices may lead to increased levels of silence within the organization. These practices are represented in two factors (Morrission & Milliken, 2000):

2.4.1.1. Managers' Fear of Negative Feedback

The top management may be afraid of getting negative feedback information from the subordinates, as it may feel threatened as a result of this information, particularly, if they involve its members personally or their work. Because of that, those members would eschew this information, and even if it reached them they would neglect it or question the credibility of the source, believing that the feedback from the bottom may be less accurate and less legitimate (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

2.4.1.2. Managers' Implicit Beliefs

Silence increases when the top management is in an ivory tower prohibiting it from seeing the actual reality because of lack of access to information, or due to welcoming the good information rather than, the negative (Van, Dyne, et al, 2003). Thus, the support of top management of silence leads employees not to talk about work issues. Besides, the administration may describe employees who talk about labor issues as problems makers (Milliken, et al., 2003).

2.4.2. Lack of Communication Opportunities

Contact is essential to the effectiveness of any organization. It represents the transfer of information verbally or using other means for the purpose of persuasion and influencing the behavior of others. Among the most important functions of the communication process is that it provides individuals with the necessary information for the purpose of decision-making, as it represents an outlet to express feelings, opinions and trends. It is an important means to satisfy social needs of individuals (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

The more contact opportunities within the organization, the greater participation and expression of opinion on issues and problems of the work, as employees have the opportunity to make suggestions, which increase the degree of career belonging and involvement of employees (Smidts, et al., 2001).

2.4.3. Support of Supervisor for Silence

The supervisor's behavior creates a microcosm climate of silence at the level of the department where he works, where subordinates do not trust that supervisors will not directly or indirectly punish them because of their talk on their mistakes in the work. Therefore, subordinates tend to silence (Spreitzer, 1996; Sugarman, 2001).

The subordinates' silence is influenced by trends and tendencies of the supervisors to silence rather than trends and tendencies of top management. Therefore, when the supervisor listens to his subordinates, they will consider him a role model, and tend to involve themselves in labor issues and talk about it. This is

because the supervisory relations have a tremendous impact on the performance and career paths of subordinates as well as on rewards from the organization (Sparrowe & Liden, 2005).

The relationship of supervisor's strength and stature to silence or talking can be analyzed in two ways: on the one hand, the subordinate may tend to talk more than keep silence with a strong supervisor, because this subordinate believes that the supervisor has the ability to resolve any problem or issue related to work. Here, subordinates find it useful to talk in the presence of supervisor who has the powers to solve work problems within the organization (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

On the other hand, the freedom to express dissenting opinion may be restricted when working under the leadership of a supervisor with prestige and power, because the subordinate tends to the option of silence due to fear of the negative impact of expressing the dissenting opinion (Turner & Pratkanis, 1998).

In spite of that, power and status of the supervisor can increase or decrease the silence of subordinates, but many researchers assert that subordinates are more sensitive to the risks of talking more than the benefits, in the presence of a strong supervisor. It can be concluded that silence could increase in the presence of a powerful supervisor (Edmondson, 1996).

2.4.4. Official Authority

Officialdom is the degree by which the activities carried out by employees are formed within the organization, through the adoption of several measures. These procedures are usually written, and associated with the presence of work evidences and records identifying the behavior of employees, the tasks to be achieved and regulations controlling the work progress within the organization (Moorhead & Criffin, 2004).

Officialdom is based on the strength of the position or location in the organizational structure. Dealing follows specific orders and a bureaucrat approach through decision-making centralization, and the use of regulations to deal with the problems and issues of work. At this point, the organization lacks an effective mechanism for information feedback. This is because there are few upwards communication channels because heads believe that the views of the subordinates are unimportant and therefore tend to silence (Ashford et al., 1998).

2.4.5. Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions

The fear of the reaction may lead employees to believe that talking about work problems might deprive them of their jobs or upgrade to higher positions within the organization (Milliken, et al, 2003).

2.5. Organizational Silence Effects

Silence affects the decision-making process of the organization, in the sense that the quality of the decision depends on the need to have knowledge of the employees' suggestions, and vice versa. Silence negatively affects the organization in the sense that it prevents information feedback, which leads to poor ability to detect and correct errors (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

There are negative impacts of organizational silence, namely (1) poor participation of employees in decision-making because of the lack of the channels or opportunities of communication, (2) reducing dealing with conflict or dispute in an effective manner, and (3) weakness of the employees' capacity to learning and self-development (Low et al ., 2002).

The effects of organizational silence are not limited to the organization. These effects are represented in (1) the individual feeling unappreciated, as he does not contribute in earnest in the issues of the organization, reducing the importance and value of his presence, (2) lack of the individual's ability to control, reducing motivations at work and participation in the issues within the organization, and (3) the individual suffering from cognitive dissonance (Hazen, 2006).

Organizational silence does have implications and consequences on the climate of trust within the organization, because it leads to poor relations of trust between employees due to lack of dialogue between them (Willman et al., 2006).

Organizational silence correlates negatively with organizational trust. This means that the more silence means less trust (Nakolaous, et al., 2011).

There are several implications of organizational silence, as silence is of a significant impact on individuals and the organization. In spite of that, the silence study results have little attention from the management literature. The employee's silence has considerable implications on the employee himself, the organization, and even the community. This is because the silent employee, regarding labor issues, prevents the flow of new information. Silence leads, in some cases, to organizational failure (Bogosian, 2012).

2.6. Organizational Success

"Success" in English, according to (Webster, 1974) means end your access to what is best, or access to excel.

In French, according to (Robert, 1983) "Reussite" means getting a new result, and the means to reach or attain higher. With respect to organizational success, there is still some confusion and lack of clarity of methodological and procedural frameworks.

Growth is an indicator for measuring organizational success. It means efficiency or the organization's ability to achieve its objectives in the long term, through expansion, renovation and survival (Whetten, 1987).

Regarding success through financial performance, operational productivity and efficiency, profits, target return, improvement programs in total quality management framework, re-engineering of reference and comparison is a narrow view that does not define success in the long-term in light of competitive markets. Success in the long-term lies in the organization's ability to do better things than competitors do. This is through owning distinct and fundamental capabilities that can not be imitated; besides ability to get on a competitive center of excellence (Hill, 2001).

Organizational success is the organization's ability to achieve long-term goals and balance between the goals and objectives of the organization of employees (Kenny, 2001).

Organizational success is the organization's ability to coordinate activities in all components linking this to a common vision to achieve its strategic goals (Dell & Kramer, 2003).

The basic elements of organizational success may be expressed in the form of an equation: organizational success = message + strategic goals + outstanding performance (Whitney, 2010).

There are two approaches for organizational success in all different organizations. The first is the economic gateway. It is based on the competitive advantage stemming from the distinct market place. The first set for the performance of the organization is the external environment of the structure of the competition environment industry (Ambrosini, 2003). This includes approaches of forces of competition (Porter), innovation (Schumpeter), and scenario analysis which is characterized by a vision of the future opportunities and environmental threats, besides forecasting analysis of the competitive advantages (Grant, 2000).

The second approach to organizational success is based on the relatively modern resources approach, which confirms the possibility of looking at the organization as a package of resources to enable them to get a sustainable competitive advantage (Ambrosini, 2003). This approach is mainly based on a study (Selznick, 1957) about the distinctive competencies, and Penrose (1959) that the organization is a collection of resources and their performance depends on their ability to use these resources. This includes the approach of the value chain to analyze the strategic capabilities that can be converted into essential competencies that support competitive advantage analysis (Hitt, 2001).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of organizational silence. There is one dependent variable of organizational success. It shows the rational links among the variables. The research model is as shown in figure (1).

The research framework suggests that organizational silence has an impact on organizational success. Organizational silence as measured consisted of support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, and subordinate's fear of negative reactions (Schechtman, 2008; Brinsfield, 2009).

Organizational success is measured in terms of organizational survival and organizational growth (Simon et al., 2011).

Figure (1)
Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

3.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between organizational silence and organizational success. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment. The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship between organizational silence and organizational success. The researcher found several indicators notably the important and vital role that could be played by organizational silence. As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between organizational silence (lack of communication opportunities) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- Q3: What is the statistically significant relationship between organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- Q4: What is the nature and extent of the statistical relationship between organizational silence (official authority) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- Q5: What is the nature of the relationship between organizational silence (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

There are studies in literature that study organizational silence and organizational success factors separately and within the frame of bilateral relation, but there is no study that examines these two factors collectively at the Egyptian environment. This study aims to contribute to the literature by examining the research variables collectively and revealing the interaction between the research variables.

As a result of the discussions given above, the following hypotheses were developed to test the effect of organizational silence on organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

- H1: Organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) of employees has no statistically significant effect on organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

- H2: Organizational silence (lack of communication opportunities) of employees has no statistically significant impact on organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- H3: Organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) of employees has no statistically significant influence on organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- H4: Organizational silence (official authority) of employees has no statistically significant relationship with organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.
- H5: Organizational silence (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) of employees has no statistically significant impact organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

3.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City. The total population is 11550 employees.

Determination of respondent sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 372 employees at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City is presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Industrial Companies	Employees	Percentage	Sample Size
1. Ezz Company for Reinforcement Steel	2100	18.2%	372X 18.2% = 68
2. Arab Company for Steel (Arco Steel)	750	6.5%	372X 6.50% = 24
3. Horizon for Investment (Geraneto)	1200	10.4%	372X 10.4% = 39
4. Egyptian-American Steel Company (Bishan)	3300	28.6%	372X 28.6% = 106
5. Al Gawhara for Ceramics	2700	23.4%	372X 23.4% = 87
6. Egyptian Group for Investments (Prima)	1500	12.9%	372X 12.9% = 48
Total	11550	100%	372X 100% = 372

Source: Personnel Department at Industrial Companies, Sadat City, Egypt, 2015

Descriptive statistics are used to describe some of the features of the respondents at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City who participated in the survey. Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Frequency Distribution Table of Demographics

Demographic Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1- Sex	Male	235	74.6%
	Female	80	25.4%
	Total	315	100%
2- Marital Status	Single	120	38.1%
	Married	195	61.9%
	Total	315	100%
3- Age	Under 30	110	34.9%
	From 30 to 45	155	49.2%
	Above 45	50	15.9%
	Total	315	100%
4- Educational Level	Secondary school	100	31.7%
	University	170	54.0%
	Post Graduate	45	14.3%
	Total	315	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	60	19.0%
	From 5 to 10	215	68.3%
	More than 10	40	12.7%
	Total	315	100%

3.4. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the relationship between organizational silence and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City. A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to organizational silence, organizational success, and demographic information of employees at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City. Data collection took two months. Survey responses were 84%, 315 completed surveys out of the 372 distributed.

3.5. Data Collection Tools

3.5.1. Organizational Silence Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by Schechtman, 2008; and Brinsfield, 2009 in measuring organizational silence, which has been divided into five elements (support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, and subordinate's fear of negative reactions).

The 27-item scale organizational silence section is based on Schechtman, 2008; and Brinsfield, 2009. There were five items measuring support of the top management of silence, six items measuring lack of communication opportunities, five items measuring support of supervisor for silence, five items measuring official authority, and six items measuring subordinate's fear of negative reactions. The survey form is used as the main tool for data collection in measuring organizational silence at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Responses are categorized using a 5-point Likert Scale for each statement, which ranges from (1) “very ineffective”, (2) “ineffective”, (3) “neither effective nor ineffective”, (4) “effective”, and (5) “very effective”.

3.5.2. Organizational Success Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by (Simon et al., 2011), in measuring organizational success, which has been divided into two main components (organizational survival and organizational growth). The 10-item scale organizational success section is based on Simon, et al., 2011. There were five items measuring organizational survival and five items measuring organizational growth. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement which ranges from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

3.6. Data Analysis

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) (MRA), and (3) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

4. Hypotheses Testing

4.1. Evaluating Reliability

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, the reliability of organizational silence and organizational success were assessed to reduce errors of measuring and maximizing constancy of these scales. To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach's alpha test was conducted.

Table (3) shows the reliability results for organizational silence and organizational success. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were therefore excellent, according to Langdridge's (2004) criteria.

Table (3) Reliability of Organizational Silence and Organizational Success

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
Organizational Silence	Support of the top Management of Silence	5	0.9500
	Lack of Communication Opportunities	6	0.9396
	Support of Supervisor for Silence	5	0.9034
	Official Authority	5	0.8814
	Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions	6	0.9063
	Total Measurement	27	0.9844
Organizational Success	Organizational Survival	5	0.9811
	Organizational Growth	5	0.9867
	Total Measurement	10	0.9907

Regarding Table (3), the 27 items of organizational silence are reliable because the ACC is 0.9844. For support of the top management of silence, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9500. Lack of communication opportunities, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9396.

Furthermore, support of supervisor for silence which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9034. For official authority, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8814. Subordinate's fear of negative reactions, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9063. Thus, the internal consistency of organizational silence can be acceptable.

According to Table (3), the 10 items of organizational success are reliable because the ACC is 0.9907. The organizational survival, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9811. The 5 items related to organizational growth are reliable because ACC is 0.9867. Thus, the reliability of organizational success can be acceptable.

Accordingly, two scales were defined, organizational silence (27 variables), where ACC represented about 0.9844, and organizational success (10 variables), where ACC represented 0.9907.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Table (4) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Constructs

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Support of the top management of silence	3.37	0.940	1					
2. Lack of communication opportunities	3.46	0.888	0.969**	1				
3. Support of Supervisor for silence	3.41	0.878	0.965**	0.940**	1			
4. Official Authority	3.49	0.824	0.977**	0.960**	0.964**	1		
5. Subordinate's fear of negative reactions	3.35	0.856	0.972**	0.974**	0.937**	0.949**	1	
6. Organizational Success	4.11	1.199	0.467**	0.459**	0.448**	0.483**	0.456**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

The researcher calculated means and standard deviations for each variable and created a correlation matrix of all variables used in hypothesis testing. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation values related to dependent and independent variables of this study and correlation coefficients between these variables are given in Table (4).

According to Table (4), the reasons of the employees remain silent was generated according to the respondents' answers. In order to determine what reasons affect employees to remain silent at work. Reasons were grouped under five factors. They are (1) support of the top management of silence, (2) lack of

communication opportunities, (3) support of supervisor for silence, (4) official authority, and (5) subordinate's fear of negative reactions.

Based on Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of organizational silence. Among the various facets of organizational silence, those who responded identified the presence of a official authority (M=3.49, SD=0.824). This was followed by lack of communication opportunities (M=3.46, SD=0.888), support of supervisor for silence (M=3.41, SD=0.879), support of the top management of silence (M=3.37, SD=0.940), and subordinate's fear of negative reactions (M=3.35, SD=0.856).

The second issue examined was the different organizational success (organizational survival, and organizational growth). Most of the respondents identified the overall organizational success (M=4.11, SD=1.199).

According to Table (4), organizational silence dimensions have negative and significant relation with organizational success dimensions. The correlation between organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) and organizational success is 0.467. For organizational silence (lack of communication opportunities) and organizational success, the value is 0.459 whereas organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) and organizational success show correlation value of 0.448. For organizational silence (official authority) and organizational success, the value is 0.483 whereas organizational silence (subordinate fear of negative reactions) and organizational success show correlation value of 0.456.

Finally, Table (4) proves that there is a significant and negative correlation between organizational silence and organizational success. So our hypothesis is supported and it can be said that there is a significant and negative correlation between organizational silence and organizational success.

4.3. Organizational Silence (Support of the top Management of Silence) and Organizational Success

The relationship between organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Table (5) MRA Results for Organizational Silence (Support of the top Management of Silence) and Organizational Success

The Variables of Organizational Silence (Support of the top Management of Silence)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Organization's management believes that its role is limited to the implementation of instructions.	0.187*	0.425	0.180
2. The organization is not interested in encouraging employees to express their opinions or suggestions concerning aspects of the work.	0.355*	0.467	0.218
3. Management of the organization does not tend to serious discussion of the views and suggestions of employees.	0.257*	0.363	0.131
4. Management of the organization does not express gratitude to workers for their opinions and suggestions for useful work.	0.291**	0.449	0.201
5. I do not feel comfortable when management of the organization is involved in solving a problem belonging to me personally.	0.048	0.434	0.188
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.503 0.253 20.884 5, 309 3.78 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (5) proves that there is a relationship between organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) and organizational success at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of support of the top management of silence can explain 25.3% of the total differentiation in organizational success level. For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of organizational silence (support of the top management of silence) and organizational success is obtained. Because MCC is 0.503, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.4. Organizational Silence (Lack of Communication Opportunities) and Organizational Success

The relationship between organizational silence (lack of communication opportunities) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between organizational silence (lack of communication opportunities) and Organizational Success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Table (6) MRA Results for organizational silence (Lack of Communication Opportunities) and Organizational Success

The Variables of Organizational Silence (Lack of Communication Opportunities)	Beta	R	R ²
1. There is no exchange of information between various departments and divisions within the organization.	0.040	0.362	0.131
2. The chances of communication between employees in other departments are not enough	0.039	0.350	0.122
3. Management of the organization does not notify the staff with the organization's important problems and issues.	0.260*	0.363	0.132
4. There is not enough channels of communication between employees and senior management of the organization.	0.205	0.423	0.178
5. Management of the organization does not bother to hold meetings to discuss issues and matters relating to work.	0.284*	0.468	0.219
6. My superiors at work do not possess the good skills needed for listening to my views and suggestions.	0.284**	0.449	0.201
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.502 0.252 17.295 3, 308 3.01 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

As Table (6) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.502. This means that organizational success has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of lack of communication opportunities.

Furthermore, the R^2 of 0.252 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 25,2%. It is evident that the five independent variables justified 25.2% of the total factors of organizational success. Hence, 74.8% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis the null hypothesis.

4.5. Organizational Silence (Support of Supervisor for Silence) and Organizational Success

The relationship between organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Table (7) proves that there is a relationship between organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) and organizational success.

As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of support of supervisor for silence can explain 23.6% of the total differentiation in organizational success level. For the results of a structural

analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of organizational silence (support of supervisor for silence) and organizational success is obtained. Because MCC is 0.486, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (7) MRA Results for Organizational Silence (Support of Supervisor for Silence) and Organizational Success

The Variables of Organizational Silence (Support of Supervisor for Silence)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I hesitate to speak freely with my direct manager concerning a problem at work.	0.151*	0.397	0.157
2. My direct manager does not care about any negative information about my performance.	0.020	0.444	0.197
3. My direct manager sees any criticism against him a sort of challenging him.	0.225	0.455	0.207
4. My direct manager suspects the source of my information concerning my performance at work.	0.219*	0.448	0.200
5. My direct manager sees the difference in opinion on the problems of working longer unhelpful.	0.085	0.171	0.029
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.486 0.236 19.109 5, 309 2.63 0.000	
* P < 0.05			

4.6. Organizational Silence (Official Authority) and Organizational Success

The relationship between organizational silence (official authority) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is: *There is no relationship between Organizational Silence (official authority) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.*

Table (8) MRA Results for Organizational Silence (Official Authority) and Organizational Success

The Variables of Organizational Silence (Official Authority)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My direct manager depends mainly on the official authority to influence subordinates.	0.137	0.425	0.180
2. My direct manager draws on the method of threatening with punishment to guide the behavior of subordinates.	0.272*	0.467	0.218
3. My direct manager accepts excuses of subordinates with difficulty when they commit negligence in their work.	0.203*	0.363	0.132
4. My direct manager directs the behavior of subordinates through compliance with laws and regulations.	0.268**	0.449	0.201
5. My direct manager complies with laws and regulations in force when solving problems of subordinates.	0.104*	0.280	0.078
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.511 0.261 21.807 5, 309 3.78 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (8) proves that there is a relationship between organizational silence (official authority) and organizational success at significance level of 0,000.

As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of official authority can explain 26.1% of the total differentiation in organizational success level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of organizational silence (official authority) and organizational success is obtained. Because MCC is 0.511, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.7. Organizational Silence (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions) and Organizational Success

The relationship between organizational silence (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between Organizational Silence (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City.

Table (9) MRA Results for Organizational Silence (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions) and organizational success

The Variables of Organizational Silence (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I feel afraid to inform my direct manager with the problems of work in the organization.	0.027	0.271	0.073
2. I don't tend to talking about the negative working conditions for fear of being held accountable.	0.462*	0.467	0.218
3. I prefer to stay silent in order to avoid conflicts or disagreements with superiors.	0.056	0.440	0.193
4. I prefer to stay silent for fear of breaking my relationships with my colleagues.	0.023	0.282	0.079
5. I prefer to stay silent not to be considered a problem-maker.	0.219*	0.367	0.134
6. My speaking of work problems could be harmful to my personal interests.	0.263**	0.449	0.201
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.492 0.242 16.403 6, 308 3.01 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.492. This means that organizational success has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of subordinate's fear of negative reactions.

Furthermore, the R^2 of 0.242 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 24.2%. It is evident that the six independent variables justified 24.2% of the total factors of organizational success. Hence, 75.8% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

5. Research Findings

The present study on analyzing the relationship between organizational silence (support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City revealed the following results:

1. There is a significant relationship between organizational silence and organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City. Organizational silence plays an important role in influencing organizational success. Also, organizational silence contributes significantly to organizational success. Hence, the top management should (1) encourage employees to talk about work issues and choosing the appropriate time for that, (2) increasing employees' exchange and circulation of

new ideas, and (3) the need to motivate employees to talk and provide their opinions and suggestions about work problems.

2. This study concluded that the organizational silence was negatively related with organizational success at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City. Overall findings from this study suggested that organizational silence does affect employees' engagement. Hence, the top management should (1) coordinate between different departments and divisions within the organization, (2) provision of good channels of communication between the employees within the organization, and (3) developing effective communication channels which support exchange and transfer of ideas and information.
3. There is a negative relationship between organizational silence and organizational success of employees at the Egyptian industrial companies in Sadat City. In other words, organizational silence affects organizational success. So, top management should (1) pay attention to the moral of the employees within the organization, (2) provide of organizational support for the exchange of ideas associated to labor issues, (3) encourage employees to creative thinking within the organization, and (4) employ and attract talented employees, especially those who have high levels of organizational commitment. This is because these employees have a high tendency to speak and participate in labor issues. Thus, organizational silence can be reduced or faced focusing on the selection and retention of this distinctive quality of the staff.

6. Research Recommendations

1. Officials should work in the organization to create a culture that will encourage employees to speak, and not to keep silent regarding all critical business issues so that we can know their problems and try to resolve them.
2. Preparation and training of administrative leaders, as the training is the mainstay of administrative development. Hence, Managers should provide an opportunity for subordinates to participate in matters relating to their work and listen to and study their views, desires, needs and then execute the good ones. Heads should pay attention to each new initiative of the workers and convince them with the interest and desire of the administration in innovation and continuous improvement in the ways and methods of work. It gives them the opportunity to participate in the administration as a kind of stimulus, encouraging participation and innovation through involvement in setting goals of the organization, the decision-making process, and determining the stage of their participation.
3. The need to increase attention and action on the coherence of the organization group, as well as the professional commitment and procedural justice because of its inverse relationship to silent workers. It has been found that the more these variables exit, the less workers keep silent.
4. Improving leadership patterns requires a scientific approach to stimulate the administrative leaders for continual good performance. This requires adopting modern systems of management, such as management by goals which achieves flexibility and freedom in performance, besides saving management time in the planning and follow-up of work. Add to this development of subordinates who are the second row capable of leadership. This is one of the important results.
5. The need for increased attention on the part of senior management to support the exchange of information and ideas with employees in the organization process because its significant correlation effect is obvious to silence workers. The civil servant who feels that his heads do not care about his views would be more silent.
6. Encouraging personal initiative of the workers by offering rewards and incentives for new ideas that contribute to the treatment of problems of the organization and help in its development.
7. Formation of specialized committees to study the proposals and issues that relate to subordinates and commitment to their recommendations.
8. Notes from the results of the study also showed significant correlation between the extent of adoption of the supervisors of the behavior of silence and silent workers. This means that supervisors ought to pay due attention to the opinions and suggestions of subordinates.
9. Paying attention to officials in the organization, including the development of effective communication channels between workers, as well as transferring their knowledge and skills to those responsible for

decision-making. This is reflected in increased confidence of senior management personnel lowering their silence about the critical issues in the organization.

10. Promote open-door policy by opening channels of communication to the subordinates to communicate their ideas to their heads, either through personal meetings, suggestion funds or regular meetings, as well as facilitating communication with higher heads in case direct head does not respond.

7. Research Implications

The findings of the study should contribute to managers and practitioners becoming more aware of ES. In addition, management should encourage employees to express their relevant ideas, information and opinions.

The cultural dimensions such as appreciating the individuals, orientation to detail, team orientation and competition may lead to silence breaking, as they urge people to actively participate in matters of the organization, which reduces the degree of silence (O.Reilly, 1991).

It is not easy to break silence climate of employees and their managers. The behavioral cycles that maintain organizational silence will be hard to break in part because they are not subject to direct observation or discussion. To prevent silence from characterizing their organizations, leaders should not only permit, but reward, employees who come forward with sensitive or risky information, and should create formal mechanisms through which employees can speak up anonymously if they wish to do so (Reichers, et al. 1997).

The nature of silence behavior makes it difficult to break. This may be due to the fact that organizational silence may be a result of lack of confidence in the organization. It may be, then, difficult to restore that trust in a short period of time. This is because breaking silence and transition from a climate of silence to one that encourages talking may need a revolutionary or radical change of system (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

Silence climate has an impact on organization's ability to detect errors and learn and, therefore, organizational effectiveness is negatively affected. ES behaviour can also create stress, cynicism, and dissatisfaction (Tamuz, 2001).

Breaking silence needs a vision which can provide a climate that helps in engagement and talking. Silence can be overcome through (1) encouraging employees to talk about work issues and choosing the appropriate time for that, (2) increasing employees' exchange and circulation of new ideas, (3) coordination between different departments and divisions within the organization, (4) provision of good channels of communication between the employees within the organization, (5) paying attention to the morale of the employees within the organization, (6) provision of organizational support for the exchange of ideas associated to labor issues, and (7) encouraging employees to creative thinking within the organization (Piderit & Ashford, 2003).

Breaking silence is also possible through the administration's desire to hear the views and suggestions of staff about problems and issues of work which they face. This is because the employee must feel safe when talking (Milliken et al., 2003).

Another way to encourage speaking up behaviour is to ensure communication opportunities and create formal systems for the transfer or exchange of information, concerns or ideas. Employees who have ideas or suggestions for improvement who do not feel that they can bring these to their bosses, could submit them to a designated person who then presents the ideas for review (Milliken et al., 2003).

Another way of breaking silence would be through the keenness of the leaders of organizations to fight or prevent any impediments to the transfer or exchange of upwards information relating to problems and issues of work (Edmondson, 2003).

Top managers and supervisors have to create a workplace where employees will feel safe to express their views and will be encouraged to offer their ideas and suggestions. Therefore, top managers and supervisors should develop attitudes and engage in behaviours that would create a psychologically safety net for their employees. (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

There are some tools that can be used for the purpose of breaking organizational silence. They are (1) the need to motivate employees to talk and provide their opinions and suggestions about work problems, (2) developing effective communication channels which support exchange and transfer of ideas and

information, and (3) the need to employ and attract talented employees especially those who have high levels of organizational commitment. This is because these employees have a high tendency to speak and participate in labor issues. Thus, organizational silence can be reduced or faced focusing on the selection and retention of this distinctive quality of the staff (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

Organizations today need not only to recruit but also to retain and motivate talented employees. Managers may consider organizational silence as an important variable when they explore organizational climate and culture or when they want to create an environment where talented people would choose to remain or wish to join. These practical implications are also important in a change context where the “truth” must be heard in order to be able to effectively implement and institutionalize the change and improve the existing situation (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

Finally, employees are regarded as major sources of change, creativity, learning, and innovation, which are critical factors to the success of organizations. However, many employees choose not to voice their opinions and concerns about matters in their organizations (Liu, et al. 2009).

8. Limitations and Future Research

There are some limitations of this study. They are (1) data was gathered from one private sector in Egypt. Therefore, the findings of this research need to be evaluated with this in mind. The survey answers are related to the perception of employees at that moment, (2) the respondents are unwilling to answer the questionnaires accurately. Therefore, before distributing questionnaires among respondents, we attempted to describe the positive effects of the results of this research on their work-life quality and satisfying their needs, (3) the current study is about cause and effect relationship among research variables; maybe there are other factors that affect research variables, which need to be identified.

There are several areas for future research. They are (1) identifying factors affect employees' silence; (2) identifying the effects of employees' silence on job satisfaction and organizational commitment (3) identifying the effects of leadership style on employees' silence, (4) identifying the effects of demographic variables on employees' silence, (5) identifying the relationship between organizational culture and organizational silence, (6) identifying the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and organizational silence, (7) identifying the relationship between organizational success and organizational silence, (8) identifying the relationship between organizational excellence and organizational silence (9) silence motivations (defensive silence, relations supportive silence, de facto silence, the silence of negligence) in service organizations, (10) the relationship between silence and organizational justice within business organizations, (11) comparing determinants of silence in the production and service organizations, and (12) the relationship between the determinants of organizational silence and work involvement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, ES is evident in many organizations. This research expanded on previous research which conceptualized ES. Based on systematic examination of subjects' reported experiences, silence does indeed appear to be more complex than can be accounted for by assuming it is equivalent to an absence of voice.

Moreover, the empirical evidence gathered makes a strong case for conceptualizing and examining organizational silence. Additionally, this research demonstrated that this covert and seemingly ambiguous phenomenon can be measured. Although more work is needed in the area of organizational silence, it appears that this research has effectively set the stage for further empirical examination.

In this research, most of the employees felt that the common reasons for ES are derived from administrative and organizational factors. They think that their ignorance or not to speak up about work-related problems and organization-based issues are because of executives' attitudes and behaviors. These results are consistent with the previous researchers who found that the most common reasons for choosing to remain silent are "administrative and organizational reasons" (Cakici, 2008).

The managers hold the key role on ES since they determine the policies and organizational decisions. They have the power to establish an internal mechanism in order to remove any administrative and organizational reasons for ES allowing employees to speak up explicitly (Cakici, 2008).

Establishing an appropriate reward system for creative ideas and facilitating development and skill-building training can break ES in organizations. Additionally, reorientation of rules, dissemination of

collaborative studies, re-structuring the harvesting of institutional knowledge and programs aimed at improving human resources management for executives are very important in minimizing the ES. Reassuring trust and rebuilding the communication bridges will help to increase the performance of an organization (Panahi et al., 2012).

Organizational silence can appear in different forms. Employees, based on acquiescence, may not express their views and opinions openly in the face of the management in the organizations; withhold their ideas intentionally because of fear or urge for self-protection or opt for remaining silence for the sake of other colleagues' well-being (Yıldız, 2013).

Organizational silence not only results in low levels of morale, lack of confidence, disloyalty, stress and employees leaving, but also constitutes a barrier to the establishment of a healthy feedback mechanism (Yıldız, 2013).

Organizational silence makes the employees feel that they are unvalued; they don't have control over their own work and suffer from dissonance, stress and burnout feeling (Nikolaou et al, 2011).

The employees are trying to make sense of self-efficacy or competency. So employees should always be asked to speak, offering views and news in order to remove organizational silence (Tahmasebi1, et al., 2013).

References

- Alparslan, A., (2010). Örgütsel Sessizlik İklimi Ve İşgören Sessizlik Davranışları Arasındaki Etkileşim: Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi Öğretim Elemanları Üzerinde Bir Araştırma', Master Thesis, University of Suleyman Demirel.
- Ambrosini V., (2003). Tacit and Ambiguous Resource as Source of Competitive Advantage, Palgrave Macmillan, UK.
- Argyris, C., (1997). Double Loop Learning in Organizations, Harvard Business Review, 55(5)11-128.
- Ashford, S., Rothbard, N., Piderit S. Dutton J., (1998). Out on a limb: The Role of Context and Impression Management in Selling Gender-Equity, Issues". Administrative Science Quarterly,43 (1), PP. 23-57.
- Bagheri, G., Zarei, R. & Nik Aeen, M. (2012), Organizational Silence (Basic Concepts and Its Development Factors), Ideal Type of management, Vol. 1, No. 1, P. 50.
- Beer M, (2009). High Commitment, High Performance Management, HBSWK.HBS.EDU.
- Beheshtifar M., Borhani H., and Moghadam, M., (2012). Destructive role of employee silence in organizational success International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, 2 (11) (2012), pp. 275–282
- Bogosian, R., (2012). Engaging Organizational Voice: A Phenomenological Study of Employee's Lived Experiences of Silence in Work Group Settings", The Faculty of Graduate School of Education and Human Development of the George Washington University.
- Bowen, F. & Blackmon, K. (2003). Spirals of silence: The dynamic effects of diversity on organizational voice, Journal of Management Studies 40(6): 1393- 1417.
- Brinsfield C., (2009). Employee Silence: Investigation of Dimensionality, Development of Measures and Examination of Related Factors. (Unpublished dissertation: The Ohio State University).
- Brinsfield C., Edwards MS, Greenberg J, (2009). Voice and Silence in Organizations: Historical Review and Current Conceptualizations. In J. Greenberg, M. S. Edwards (Eds.), Voice and Silence in Organizations (pp. 3-33). UK: Emerald Group Publishing LTD.
- Çakici A (2010). Örgütlerde iç goren sessizligi, neden sessiz kalmayi tercih ediyoruz?". Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.
- Cakici, A. (2008). A research on issues, causes and perceptual results of silence at organizations, Cukurova University Journal of Social Science, 17(1), 117- 134.
- Collis, David & Montgomery, Cynthia (1995), "Competing on Resources", Harvard Business Review, Vol.22, July-August 1995: 118-128
- Daniel W., (1999). Biostatistics: A Foundation For Analysis in the Health Sciences, 7th Ed, New York, John Wiley & Sons.
- Dell, D., and Kramer, R., (2003). Forging Strategic Business Alignment", The conference board, www.conferenceboard.org.

- Edmondson, A. (2003), “Speaking up in the operating room: How team leaders promote learning in interdisciplinary action teams”, *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 40 No. 6, 1419-52.
- Edmondson, A., (1996). Learning from Mistakes is Easier than Done: Group and Organizational Influence on the Detection and Correction of Human Error, *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*,32(1), PP. 5.28
- Ellis, J. Dyne, L. (2009). Voice and silence as observers’ reactions to defensive voice: Prediction based on communication competence theory, pp. 37-61. In Greenberg,M.S. Edwards (Ed.). *Voice and Silence in organizations*.
- Gambarotto, F and Cammozzo. A., (2010). Dreams of Silence Employee Voice and Innovation in a Public Sector Community of Practice, *Innovation, Management, Policy& Practice* ,12(2)166-179.
- Grant, R., (2000). *Contemporary Strategy Analysis*, Oxford, UK.
- Hazen, M., (2006). Silence, Perinatal Loss and olyphony: a post Modern perspective. *Journal of organizational change management*, 19(2), 237-249.
- Henriksen, K. and E. Dayton (2006). Organizational silence and hidden threats to patient safety, *Health Services Research*, 41 (4), Part II, 1539- 1554.
- Hitt, M., Bierman, L., Shimizu, K., & Kochhar, R. (2001). Direct and moderating effects of human capital on strategy and performance in professional service firms: A resource-based perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44: 13–28.
- Kahn W., (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Admin. Sci. Q.* 33(4), 692-724.
- Karacaoglu, K. and A. Cingoz (2008). Örgütsel Sessizlik. Ozdevecioglu, M. and H. Karadal (Ed.), Örgütsel Davranışta Seçme Konular, Ankara, 155-167.
- Kenny, G. (2001). *Strategic Factor: Developing and Measure Winning Strategy*, 1st Ed., President Press, National Library of Australia.
- Korsgaard, M., Meglino, B. and Lester, S. (1997). Beyond Helping: Do Other-Oriented Values Have Broader Implications In Organizations?” *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 82, 160-77.
- Lawler, E., (1992). “The Ultimate Advantage: Creating The High-Involvement Organization”. San Francisco: Jossey-Base pp:17-20.
- Liu, D., Wu, J. and Ma, J. (2009), Organizational silence, a survey on employees working in a telecommunication company. *IEEE Xplore.ieee.org*. P. 1647.
- Lowe, L, Mills, A., and Mullen, J., (2002). Gendering The Silences: Psycho, Gender and Organizations Studies, *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 17 (5), PP. 422 – 434.
- Milliken F, Morrison E, and Hewlin P (2003). An exploratory study of employee silence: Issues that employees don’t communicate upward and why. *J. Manage. Stud.* 40(6):1453-1476.
- Moorhead G & Griffin, R, (2004). *Organizational Behavior, Managing People and Organization*, 7th Ed., New York, Houghton, Mifflin Company.
- Morrison E, and Milliken F., (2000). Organizational silence: A barrier to change and development in a pluralistic World. *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 25(4):706-725.
- Morrison E. and Milliken F. (2003). Speaking up, remaining silent: The dynamics of voice and silence in organizations. *J. Manage. Stud.* 40(6):1353-1358..
- Nenette, B., (2002). The View From Taft, *Business World*, Manila , May (1).
- Nikmaram, S., Yamchi, H. G., Shojaii, S., Zahrani, M. A., & Alvani, S. M. (2012). Study on relationship between organizational silence and commitment in Iran. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 17(10), 1271-1277.
- Nikolaou, I, Vakola, M., & Bourantas, D. (2011). The role of silence on employees’attitudes “the day after” a merger. *Personnel Review*, 40 (6), 723-741
- O. Reilly, C. A., (1991). *Organizational Behavior: Where We're Going-* in M.R. Rosenzweig & L.W.Porter (Eds), *annual Review of Psychology* (Vol.42,PP. 427-458). Palo Alto, CA: Annual Reviews.
- Ozdemir, L., Sarioglu and Ugur, S. (2013). The evaluation employees’ organizational voice and silence perceptions in terms of demographic characteristics: A study in public and private sector. 27 (1), 257-281.

- Panahi, P., Veisehb, S., Divkhar, S. and Kamarid, F. (2012), An empirical analysis on influencing factors on organizational silence and its relationship with employee's organizational commitment, *Management Science Letters*, Vol. 2, P. 735.
- Perlow, L., Reppenning N., (2009), "The Dynamics Of Silencing Conflict", *Research In Organizational Behaviour*, Issues: 20, pp: 1-29.
- Piderit, S & Ashford, S.,(2003). Breaking Silence: Tactical Choices Women Managers Make in Speaking Up About Gender-Equity, *Journal of Management Studies*, 40 (6).
- Pinder, C. and Harlos, H., (2001). Employee Silence: Quiescence and Acquiescence As Response to Perceived Injustice, *Research in Personnel and Human Research Management*, 20, PP. 331-369.
- Podsakoff, P., McKenzie, S., Paine, J. and Bachrach D. (2000). Organizational Citizenship Behaviours: A Critical Review of the Theoretical and Empirical Literature and Suggestions for the Future Research", *Journal Management*, 26, pp: 513-563.
- Reichers, A. E. Wanous, J.P., & Austin, J.T. (1997), Understanding and managing cynicism about organizational change. *Academy of Management Executive*, Vol.11 No.1 P.48.
- Robbins, S and Judge, T., (2013). *Organizational Behavior*, Pears Education, Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- Robert P., (1983). *Brodard et Taupin*, Paris. France.
- Rodriguez, R (2004). Overcoming organizational silence: leveraging polyphony as a mean for positive change". *Midwest Academy Management Proceedings*, pp. 5-7.
- Schechtman ,G., (2008). When Silence speaks louder than words: Computer-mediated communications and perceived ostracism", PhD, Washington State University.
- Simon, A., Kumar, V., Schoeman, P., Moffat, P., Power, D., (2011). Strategic capabilities and their relationship to organizational success and its measures: Some pointers from five Australian studies", *Management Decision*, Vol. 49 No. 8, PP. 305 - 1326
- Smidts, A., Pruyn, A. and Van Riel, C. (2001). The impact of employee communication and perceived external prestige on organizational identification", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 44 No. 5, pp. 1051-63.
- Sparrowe, R & Linden, R, (2005). Two Routes to Influence: Integrating Leader-Member Exchange and Network Perspectives. *Administrative Science Quarterly*,50,505-535.
- Spreitzer, G., (1996). Social Structural Characteristics of Psychological Empowerment, *Academy of management Journal*.Vol.39,483-504.
- Sugarman, B. (2001), "A learning-based approach to organizational change: some results and guidelines", *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 62-76.
- Tahmasebi1, F., Sobhanipour, S., Aghaziarati, M., (2013). Burnout; Explaining the Role of Organizational Silence and Its Influence: Case study: Selected Executive Organizations of Qom Province, *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 3(8), PP. 272-282.
- Tamuz, M. (2001), "Learning disabilities for regulators: the perils of organizational learning in the air transportation industry", *Administration and Society*, Vol. 3, pp. 276-302.
- Tangirala S, Ramanujam R (2008). Employee silence on critical work issues: The cross level effects of procedural justice climate. *Personnel Psychology* 61:37-68.
- Tikici, M., Derin, N., & Kalkın, G. (2011). Örgütsel sessizliğin duygusal tükenmişliğe etkisi. 7.Kobi'ler ve Verimlilik Kongresi Bildiri Kitabı, T.C. İstanbul Kültür Üniversitesi Yayınları Yayın No: 155.
- Turner, M and Pratkanis, A., (1998). A Social Identity Maintenance Model of Group Think. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*,37, 210-235.
- Vakola, M., and Bouradas, D., (2005). Antecedents and consequences of organizational silence: an empirical investigation, *Employee Relations*, 27 (5), PP. 441-458
- Van Dyne, L., Ang, S. and Botero, I. (2003). Conceptualizing employee silence and employee voice as multidimensional constructs", *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 40 No. 6, pp. 1359-92.
- Weber, P. and Weber, J. (2001). Changes in employee perceptions during organisational change", *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 22, pp. 291-300.
- Webster's Merriam Co. (1974), USA.
- Whetten, D., (1987). Organizational Growth and Decline Processes, *Annual Review of Sociology*, Vol.13, PP. 335-358.

- Whitney, D., (2010). Appreciative Inquiry: Creating Spiritual Resonance in the Workplace, *Journal of Management, Spirituality & Religion* – publication pending, PP.1-21.
- Willman, P., Bryson, A. and Gomez, R. (2006) 'The Sound of Silence: Which Employers Choose 'no voice' and why?', *Socio-Economic Review*, 4: 283-299
- Willman, P., Bryson, A. and Gomez, R. (2006) 'The Sound of Silence: Which Employers Choose 'no voice' and why?', *Socio-Economic Review*, 4: 283-299
- Yıldız, E., (2013). Enigma of Silence in Organizations: What Happens To Whom and Why?, *Beykent University Journal of Social Sciences*, 6 (2), PP. 30-44.
- Zehir, C. and Erdogan, E. (2011). The Association between Organizational Silence and Ethical Leadership through Employee Performance”, *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 24, pp 1389- 1404.
- Zerubavel, E. (2006). *The elephant in the room: Silence and denial in everyday life*. New York: NY, Oxford University Press.
- Zhou, J. and George, J. (2001). When job satisfaction leads to creativity: Encouraging the expression of voice”, *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 44 No. 4, pp. 682-97.